

AI-PRISM

D3.2 – AI-PRISM Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform (I)

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
WP	Work Package
T	Task
AI	Artificial intelligence
CI	Continuous Integration
CD	Continuous Development/Deployment
2D/3D/6D	Two/three/six Dimensions

The AI-PRISM project

AI-PRISM will provide industrial users with **human-centred artificial intelligence (AI)-based solutions to create a more efficient, resilient, digital, sustainable and high-quality European manufacturing industry.**

To do so, we will develop an **integrated and scalable environment** with solutions adapted to dynamic and unpredictable manufacturing scenarios that require tasks that are difficult to automate and where speed and versatility are essential to meet users' needs. Furthermore, the solutions will be specific to semi-automated and collaborative manufacturing in flexible production processes and will not require specific robotic programming skills.

Our solutions ecosystem will have four main pillars:

1. **A human-centred collaborative robotic platform** oriented to ease hard-to-automate manufacturing tasks.
2. **A human-robot cooperative environment** powered by trustworthy AI.
3. **Social human-agent-robots teams' collaboration** — AI-based safety monitoring and robot control mechanisms to detect and avoid unsafe situations and ensure social and physical safety.
4. **An open-access network portal** to offer compliant infrastructure.

To evaluate our solutions' performance, transferability, scalability and large-scale deployment, we will perform demonstrations in real operating environments. Specifically, in **four user pilots involving key manufacturing sectors** — furniture, food/beverage, built-in appliances and electronics —, **types of robots and industrial processes that are difficult to automate, plus a generic demonstration facility.**

In addition to seeking quantitative improvements in the manufacturing sector, **AI-PRISM aims to use technological innovation to support a paradigm shift in which AI, robotics and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) are integrated into the manufacturing domain for the improvement of flexible production processes**, becoming a viable and widespread alternative for European factories.

During the next three years, **25 partners** from **12 countries** will join forces to make AI-PRISM a reality. From educational institutions to research and technology organisations, robot manufacturers, industries and use case providers; our interdisciplinary consortium brings together all the actors of the human-robot collaboration value chain and involves key experts in SSH, standardisation, exploitation, and dissemination.

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1. Introduction

1.1. OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

Deliverable describes consecutive releases of the AI-PRISM software which includes libraries for real time communication, ambient digitalization, and simulation. This includes code repositories, and pipelines to support the development of new modules, their deployment and testing. The simulation platform supports specific developed modules for agent simulation and for collaboration and risks evaluation.

The following specific objectives are targeted in WP3:

- Design and validation of a robotic framework based on ROS for the integration of the technological modules.
- A digitalization module able to map the environment from pre-existing data-models and different sensors in the environment.
- Design a unified AI-PRISM Data Model will be developed describing data flows, offering access to topics and data management functions.
- Develop a new simulation platform that will enable the simulation of specific production plants or lines. including the interaction between existing agents will be developed.

STATUS GUIDELINES

Status	Description
Planned	Task defined and assigned to an Epic
In progress	Task under current development
Ready to test	Task developed and ready to be tested
Completed	Task finished and tested
On hold	Task temporary paused

2. Architecture of the Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform

All modules below are developed as part of WP3 – Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform.

Repository is available:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3>

3. Modules

3.1. Collaborative Multiagent ROS based Robotic framework (IKE)

The Gitlab software repository is available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework>

3.1.1. ROS Framework – RF (IKER)

Module name		ROS Framework		
General description		The ROS Framework acts as a nexus between all the different devices and modules required to command a robot. Ranging from the controller that gathers data, to the controller that conducts the robot, including any module involved in the tasks in between, them being, data treatment, path planning, IA algorithms, etc...		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/ros2_base		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st 2023	It includes the docker-compose files to deploy said image as well	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compatible with amd_x64 devices • Added deployment documentation. 	Completed

		as a network to allow other modules to easily connect to it.		
3.0	TBD	It includes the docker-compose files to deploy the non-development image.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compatible with arm_x64 devices 	In progress
4.0	TBD	Dynamic docker image creator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allows for dynamic creation of docker images for Kubernetes deployment 	In progress

3.1.2. Base Hardware – BH (IKER)

Module name		Base Hardware		
General description		Interfaces to control base hardware. Other modules will use these interfaces to manage and interact with hardware devices		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st 2023	Documentation regarding Oculus Touch support for ubuntu systems added. Sawyer robot image added by combining a ROS1 image, a ROS2 image and ROS-bridge.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oculus Touch documentation • ROS2 support for sawyer robot and Docker-compose file to deploy it • ROS2 support for RealSense sensor and Docker-compose file to deploy it 	Completed

		RealSense image added.		
3.0	TBD	Continuous integration of drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for more drivers 	In progress
4.0	TBD	Dynamic docker image creator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allows for dynamic creation of docker images for Kubernetes deployment 	In progress

3.2. **Ambient digitalization for Human-Robot Collaboration (FBK)**

The Gitlab software repository is available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ambient-digitalization>

3.2.1. **Ambient sensing infrastructure – AS (FBK)**

Module name		Ambient sensing infrastructure		
General description		Interfaces to control sensing infrastructure equipment. Communication modules will manage and exchange information with sensing hardware devices using these interfaces		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ambient-digitalization/ambient-sensing-infrastructure		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st 2023	Drivers containerized providing compatibility with ROS2, for the RealSense and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RealSense driver added • UAM05LP driver added • Intrinsic camera calibration tool 	Completed

		the UAM05LP sensors. A tool to intrinsically calibrate generic cameras has also been provided.		
3.0	TBD	ROS2 compatible tool to determine the position of a camera when a reference is placed in front of it.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extrinsic calibration tool 	In progress
4.0	September 9 th 2024	-		-

3.2.2. Ambient Digitalization Modules – AD (FBK)

Module name		Ambient Digitalization Modules		
General description		Interfaces to integrate ambient digitalization modules into the ROS framework		
Gitlab link				
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	TBD	ROS implementations of the digitalization tools for each of the use case pilots.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VIGO digitalization • SIL hood digitalization • AW chairs digitalization 	In progress
3.0	March 31 st 2024	-	-	-

4.0	September 9 th 2024	Dockerized version of the FBK chair detection demo	Support for the deprecated L515 realsense camera	Completed
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3.3. Real-Time communications for sensor and platform integration and control (WINGS)

The Gitlab software repository is available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications>

3.3.1. Communications Modules – CM (IKER)

Module name		Communications Modules		
General description		Device Management interfaces to manage robots and ambient sensing infrastructure devices in the ambient from AI-PRISM. The IIoT Platform will use these interfaces to manage devices and communications with higher layers in a centralized way		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications/communications_modules		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	March 31 st 2024	This module captures any message streamed through a ROS2 topic starting with /mqtt/ and streams it through an MQTT topic to the IIoT platform.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MQTT bridge image added 	Completed
3.0	TBD	Add dynamic support for other kinds of messages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic support for non-predefined messages. 	In progress

4.0	September 9 th 2024	-	•	-
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3.3.2. Real Time Communications Network (HMI) Modules – HI (ITI)

Module name		Real Time Communications Network (HMI) Modules		
General description		Interfaces to manage and control communications network equipment. The IIoT Platform will use these (northbound) interfaces of real time communications infrastructure to manage QoS in the network.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications/real-time-communications-network-modules		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	March 31 st 2024	This module connects a software-defined wireless sensor network and an orchestration system. The wireless sensor network gathers data and shares it through a set of MQTT brokers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SD-IWSN Southbound • MQTT bridge 	Completed
3.0	TBD	First release of the SDN controller, integrated with orchestration capabilities for wireless devices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDN Controller • Resource allocation • Northbound API 	Completed
4.0	September 9 th 2024	Second release of the SDN controller, with low layer device	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDN Controller • Southbound API 	In progress

		configuration and management.		
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3.3.3. IIoT Platform – IP (WINGS)

Module name		IIoT Platform		
General description		Interfaces to Control equipment from higher-level reasoning modules. Higher-level reasoning modules will use these interfaces to define or update scheduled tasks, control rules or constraints		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications/iiot-platform_ip_wings		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	TBD	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	In progress
2.0	December 31 st 2023	-		-
3.0	March 31 st 2024	-		-
4.0	September 9 th 2024	-		-

3.3.4. Data Platform – DS (WINGS)

Module name		Data Platform		
General description		The Data Platform provides centralised batch and streaming services to access data through these interfaces		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.3-real-time-communications/data-platform		
Released versions				

Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st 2023	Added video streaming module that gathers any topic streaming images and publishes it into the MQTT server.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WINGSChariot 	Completed
3.0	March 31 st 2024	-		-
4.0	September 9 th 2024	-		-

3.4. Collaborative Simulation Platform (TAU)

The Gitlab software repository is available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.4-collaborative-simulation-platform>

3.4.1. Simulation Environment – SE (TAU)

Module name	Simulation Environment
General description	Tool that allows photorealistic 3D representations of a collaborative manufacture environment, including robots, industrial equipment, and human agents. It will help industrial partners to simulate processes in a more realistic way, considering human operators in the simulation. With the SE, users will be able to recreate production plants and lines, taking into consideration interactions between the existing agents in the environment and integrating human avatars.
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/t3.4-collaborative-simulation-platform/simulation-environment-se-tau
Released versions	

Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional Gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	31 st March 2024	First release of the database structure (SQLite) of the Simulation Environment and the front-end of the HRPI (Human-Robot Physical Interaction) module based on Nvidia Omniverse.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database creation • Front-end of the HRPI module based provided mock-ups 	Completed
3.0	9 th September 2024	First release of the back-end of the HRPI module. First integration of photo-realistic digital human workers.	First release of photo-realistic digital human workers in the scene with their animations. Functionality that allows the scene configuration.	Completed
4.0	TBD	Second release of the back-end of the HRPI module with its functionalities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Back-end of HRPI module 	In progress

4. Conclusions

4.1.1. SUMMARY

The report describes the software versions and their status in a tabular manner.

4.1.2. **NEXT STEPS**

The next versions of deliverable will contain descriptions of subsequent versions of the software and new ones if they have not been created yet.